

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL FORMULATION ON
STREPTOZOTOCIN INDUCED MEMORY IMPAIRMENT IN
RATS****Adiba Afreen^{1*}, Dr. Anil Kumar Middha²**^{1*} Research Scholar, Department of Pharmacy, Sunrise University, Alwar, Rajasthan.² Professor, Department of Pharmacy, Sunrise University, Alwar, Rajasthan.**Abstract:**

Mild to severe memory impairments can lead to neurodegenerative illnesses and/or brain damage. Alzheimer's disease (AD) is characterized by the degeneration of neurons and is incurable. This study aimed to investigate the memory-enhancing potential of an Ayurvedic polyherbal formulation (PHF) in experimental animal models of memory loss caused by streptozotocin. Three plant extracts— *Adoxa moschatellina*, *Alpinia galanga*, *Laurus nobilis* along with other excipients were suspended in a polyherbal formulation (PHF). The effectiveness of polyherbal formulation (PHF) in the learning and memory processes of animals was assessed using a variety of behavioral animal models, including the Morris water maze (MWM) test, the Elevated plus maze (EPM) test, the Pole Climbing Test (PCT), and the Social Recognition Test (SRT). The results showed that the PHF injection considerably ($P < 0.01$) shortened the duration of social recognition during trial 2 (SIT2). PHF medication considerably ($P < 0.01$) decreased the $[F(4, 20) = 6.9]$ delay to reach the concealed platform from session 3 in the MWM (Morris Water Maze) test. In a similar way, PHF proved successful in the EPM (Elevated Plus Maze) and pole climbing tests. According to RT-PCR data, p53 controls the expression of the Bcl-2 family of proteins, which was significantly lower in PHF (200 mg/kg) in the particular experiment. The proteins GAP-43, NR1, and NR2B reduce the damage to brain cells. PHF may therefore be a useful formulation for the learning and memory process in order to counteract the memory impairment caused by STZ.

Key words: *Adoxa moschatellina*, *Alpinia galanga*, *Laurus nobilis*, Pole climbing test, Elevated plus maze, Social recognition test.

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Please cite this article in press **Adiba Afreen et al., Evaluation Of Polyherbal Formulation On Streptozotocin Induced Memory Impairment In Rats., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (10).**

INTRODUCTION:

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is characterized by the degeneration of neurons, and the illness has no known effective treatment or cure.¹ It has had an impact on around 40 million individuals worldwide, and in the years to come, that number is anticipated to rise.² Individuals experiencing cognitive impairments are in a transitional phase between age-related decline and other Alzheimer's disease-related clinical conditions.³ Acquisition, consolidation, and retrieval are all related to minor to severe memory impairments, which can lead to neurodegenerative illnesses and/or brain damage.⁴

One possible first step towards mainstream therapy for the condition is to reduce the disease's development. Thus, in addition to evaluating novel medications, study into the mechanism and cause of disease is necessary. The drugs used to treat cognitive impairment may have a number of negative effects in addition to other issues. Due to their long history of neuroprotective and brain-boosting medications without adverse effects, medicinal plants and natural supplements have been the subject of intensive study in an effort to prevent these undesirable pharmacological effects. Medicinal herbs have been utilized to improve a variety of cognitive functions, including intellect, motivation, memory, and focus⁵. They are also known as nootropics, because they improve motor control, learning, emotional stability, and cognitive function.⁶

Ayurveda, an age-old Indian medical system, is becoming more well-known around the world for its emphasis on improving health and preventing disease.⁷ In this study, three traditional herbs *Laurus nobilis* were combined to create an Ayurvedic polyherbal combination. The aforementioned herbs were chosen for their folk medicine properties that improve memory and cognitive function. *Alpinia galanga*, a well-known medicinal plant of the *Zingiberaceae* family, with a somewhat spicy scent.⁸ In Asian nations, it has been utilized to treat oxidative stress, microbiological and insecticidal infections, spasms, ulcers, diarrhea, stomachaches, and diabetic mellitus.⁹ It belongs to the edible group and is a well-liked nervine tonic plant in India. The plant *Laurus nobilis* has a number of bioactive chemicals, including cineole, α -terpinyl acetate, α -pinene, β -elemene, sabinene, β -phellandrene, bornyl acetate, and camphene; those in the twig were 1,8-cineole, α -terpinyl acetate, that have anticancer, hepatoprotective, immunomodulatory, and neuroprotective properties.^{10,11} Native to India, *Laurus nobilis* has long been utilized as a neuroprotective and memory-

enhancing herb. since ancient times.¹² It belongs to family *Lauraceae* and used in the treatment of diabetes, ulcer, anxiety, liver diseases and oxidative stress.^{13,14}

Consequently, the effectiveness of Polyherbal Formulation (PHF) in improving memory was assessed in this study using several behavioral models, with an eye on the neurodevelopmental causes of memory deficit disorders such schizophrenia, dementia, Alzheimer's disease, and autism. Furthermore, to assess the enzymatic levels and the level of the metabolic enzyme acetylcholinesterase (AChE) in order to determine the biochemical levels of Polyherbal formulation (PHF) in the brain.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Chemicals and reagents

We bought the following products from Sigma Aldrich in the USA: donepezil, streptozotocin, propyl paraben, methyl paraben, tween 80, and sodium carboxymethyl cellulose. Throughout the investigation, pure water was employed, and all other solvents were of analytical quality. To assess the impact of poly herbal formulation (PHF) in several experiment models, albino Wistar rats were employed.

Preparation of formulation made up of herbs

Adoxa moschatellina (AM) *Alpinia galanga* (AG), and *Laurus nobilis* (LN) extracts were combined to make 0.5014 g, 0.3343 g, and 0.3343 g of the herbal formulation, respectively. Parabens (Propyl paraben, 0.02%, w/v and Methyl paraben, 0.2%, w/v), tween 80 (0.1%, w/v), and a small amount of sodium carboxy methylcellulose (0.5%, w/v) were then added. The mixture was then evenly triturated to create a smooth paste. To achieve suspension, the paste was vortexed with a mechanical stirrer set at 500 rpm after being washed with 100 cc of distilled water. The formulation proved to be stable for ninety days in storage.

Experimental design and drug administrations

In experimental models of memory impairment brought on by the injection of streptozotocin (STZ), the effects of extracts from *Adoxa moschatellina* (AM), *Alpinia galanga* (AG) and *Laurus nobilis* (LN) and their formulation were assessed. For 14 days, the test medication was administered together with the standard and vehicle. Before the test medication was administered, intracerebroventricular (ICV) streptozotocin (STZ) was administered.

Streptozotocin (STZ) induced memory impairment and grouping of animals

Behavioral evaluations were conducted starting on the fourteenth day following the administration of the standard medication and test compounds for a total of fourteen days. The animals were put to sleep with ether, and on the first and third day, STZ (3 mg/kg) was administered intracerebroventricularly (ICV). The Hamilton microliter syringe was fitted with a hypodermic needle for intracerebroventricular (ICV) injections. Animals' skulls were punctured perpendicularly to allow the needle to enter their brains. Fresh streptozotocin (STZ) was made by dissolving it in a solution of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) at a concentration of 25 mg/ml. The concentration was changed such that one injection would only contain the necessary 10 μ l of medication.

Seven groups of six animals each were created from the separated animals. First group: control, vehicle treated (p.o.); second group: toxic group, STZ (i/p); third group: donepezil (5 mg/kg, i/p); fourth, fifth, and sixth groups: extract of AM, AG, and LN, respectively, at a dose of 200 mg/kg, p.o.; and seventh and eighth groups: PHF (200 and 400 mg/kg, p.o., respectively).

Assessment of learning and memory

Social recognition test (SRT)

Male Wistar rats weighing between 220 and 240 grams were used for the Social Recognition Test (SRT). Administration caused memory impairment in the animals. Male Wistar rats weighing between 220 and 240 grams were used for the Social Recognition Test (SRT). The treatment of STZ damaged the memory of the animals. On the fourteenth day, the test animals were given STZ. Test drug effects were ascertained by placing an unknown adolescent in the cages of animals as social stimulation. The test animal spent five minutes with the young before the juvenile and the test animal were recorded as T1. Rat was taken out. When the same juvenile was placed back into their cages, T2 was measured two hours later. The test animal's SRT was ascertained by seeing a noteworthy decrease in contact duration during trial 2 (T2) in comparison to trial 1 (T1).

The recognition index (RI) was calculated using following formula= $RI = T2/T1$

Morris water maze (MWM) test

Male Wistar rats weighing between 220-240 g were used for the Morris Water Maze (MWM) experiment. On the fourteenth day of therapy, STZ was administered, which affected the animals' memory¹⁵. In order to set up this test, the rats were placed in a circular water-filled pool of 45 $\times$ 26 $\times$ 20 cm. The pool was labeled N-E-ES-WN, which are four

distinct beginning positions. If the animals couldn't get out of the water in 120 seconds, they may stay for 30 seconds. Each animal received the previous trials; four trials were administered daily for five days prior to the animals being placed in the pool. The animals' escape latency time was used to gauge the impact of the test medications.

Pole climbing test (PCT)

Animals with STZ-induced memory impairment were subjected to test chemicals using Cook's pole climbing device. The device has a sound box, dim light, and chamber measuring 25 cm by 25 cm by 40 cm. The animals received an electric shock via the chamber's grid floor. The animals jumped atop the pole to escape being stimulated by electricity. It was observed that the animals used this leaping as a means of escape to prevent foot shock. But getting onto the pole before being shocked because of a buzzer sound was seen as avoiding the shock. The study was concluded following ten trials spaced thirty seconds apart. Following the appropriate therapy, the animals underwent the test process once more for five days in a row.

Elevated plus maze (EPM) test

Utilizing the Elevated Plus Maze (EPM) testing device, test substances were examined for their impact on an animal model of STZ-induced memory impairment. The device is made up of two arms that are open and two that are closed, measuring 16 by 5 cm and 16 by 5 cm and 12 cm, respectively. The equipment is positioned 25 centimeters above the ground. The animals were positioned on the open arm of the EPM, and the amount of time it took them to travel between the arms was recorded. This period of time was referred to as transfer latency (TL). If TL gently pressed one of the two arms, TL was given 90 seconds. After ten seconds of use on the EPM, the animals were permitted to return to the cages. After the completion of first day trial the memory retention of animals was examined.¹⁷

Biochemical estimation

Malondialdehyde (MDA) estimation

Malondialdehyde was calculated using Colado et al., 1997's methodology. In short, brain homogenate was combined with TCA, HCl (5N), and 2% TBA. After 15 minutes of heating the mixture to 90°C, it was centrifuged for 10 minutes at 12000 $\times$ g. With an ELISA plate reader (Biotek, USA), the supernatant was separated and its wavelength was measured at 532 nm. The MDA found in the supernatant was reported in terms of nmoles/mg of protein. Tetra ethoxy propane's (TEP) standard curve was used to compute it.¹⁸

Glutathione (GSH) estimation

Animal glutathione levels were assessed using Sharm and Gupta's (2001) methodology. In summary, brain homogenate was combined 1:1 with trichloroacetic acid and centrifuged at $12000 \times g$ for 10 minutes. After being divided and combined, the supernatant (0.01ml) a combination of phosphate buffer (0.2 ml, pH 8.5), distilled water (0.04 ml), and 5,5-dithiobis (2-nitrobenzoic acid) (0.05 ml). After vortexing, the mixture was measured at 412 nm using an ELISA plate reader (Biotek, USA). GSH in the supernatant was measured and represented as $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ of protein.¹⁹

Acetylcholine (AChE) activity assay

The approach of Das et al., 2001 was used to measure acetylcholine (AChE) activity in animal brains. Using an ELISA plate reader (Biotek, USA), the activity of AChE was measured at 412 nm and expressed in $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$ protein.¹⁹

Statistical analysis

Results are expressed as mean $\pm$ S.E.M. Statistical analysis was carried out by One-way ANOVA and after that dunnett's multiple comparison assay was

done. The results were significantly different at $*p<0.05$, $**p<0.01$ and $***p<0.001$ in comparison to control group.

RESULTS:

Effect of PHF using SRT on memory animals

On the fourteenth day following STZ injection-induced memory impairment, the impact of PHF was assessed. The SRT for trial 2 was lower in treated animals than in the control group, according to the results, when compared to trial 1 SRT. As seen in Figure 1, the commonly used medication donepezil also shields rats against STZ-induced memory impairment. When AM, LN, and AG extracts were administered at 200 mg/kg, there was a substantial decrease in SIT2 ($P<0.01$) when compared to SIT1, which suggests that STZ-induced memory impairment is prevented. PHF prevented STZ-induced memory impairment better than individual plant extracts. Additionally, difference in the recognition index of control, vehicle and STZ group, confirming impairment of memory (Figure 2). The recognition index was significantly lower in donepezil, plant extracts and PHF treated groups in comparison to memory impaired group.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Memory enhancement effect of PHF using MWM test

When comparing the fourth and fifth sessions to the first, there was a noticeable drop in latency time for both the vehicle and control groups (Figure 3). Rats' memory was impaired by STZ injection by ICV, as seen by the lack of a discernible decrease in latency time until session 5. Memory impairment was averted by treatment with the usual medication donepezil, as evidenced by a considerable decrease in latency time from the third session compared to the first. Plant extracts helped rats with STZ-induced memory impairment at a dosage of 200 mg/kg. While LN greatly reduced latency time during the fifth session relative to the first, AM and AG significantly lowered latency time throughout the fourth and fifth sessions. For all groups, there was no discernible difference in the latency times between sessions 1 ($P > 0.05$) and 2 ($P > 0.05$) (Figure 3). Results indicated that starting in session 3, PHF reduced the time it took for animals to arrive at the platform.

Fig. 3

Effect of PHF on STZ induced memory impairment in pole climbing test

The latency time of treated animals was significantly reduced on days 4 and 5, according to the results, whereas no significant reduction was observed in the STZ group on any of the days. From day three forward, the usual medication donepezil significantly reduced the delay time, suggesting that STZ-induced memory impairment was prevented. Reduction in latency time on day 4 and 5 of STZ-induced memory impairment was seen after treatment with extracts of AM, AG, and LN. Nevertheless, there was no difference seen in the day 1 latency time ($P > 0.05$) across all groups (Figure 4). Additionally, the PHF dramatically reduced the latency time in rats given STZ injections starting on day 3.

Fig. 4

Effect of PHF on STZ induced memory impairment in EPM test

The latency time of treated animals was significantly reduced on days 4 and 5, according to the results, whereas no significant reduction was observed in the STZ group on any of the days. From day three forward, the usual medication donepezil significantly reduced the delay time, suggesting that STZ-induced memory impairment was prevented. Reduction in latency time on day 4 and 5 of STZ-induced memory impairment was seen after treatment with extracts of AM, ALN, and G. Nevertheless, there was no difference seen in the day 1 latency time ($P > 0.05$) across all groups (Figure 4). Additionally, the PHF dramatically reduced the latency time in rats given STZ injections starting on day 3.

Figure - 5

Biochemical estimations

Effect of PHF on MDA level in STZ-induced amnesic rat brain

Compared to the control and vehicle groups, the memory impaired rats' brain and hippocampal areas had considerably higher levels of MDA. When compared to the STZ group, donepezil treatment dramatically decreased MDA levels in both brain regions. Rats injected with STZ had much lower MDA levels in their cortex and hippocampal regions after receiving 200 mg/kg of plant extracts. In the cortex and hippocampus of the rat brain that had received a STZ injection, PHF therapy likewise significantly reduced the MDA level (Figure 6).

Fig. 6

Effect of PHF on GSH level in memory impaired rats

The impact of PHF was computed by utilizing the calibration curve produced with various glutathione concentrations to estimate the amount of GSH in rat brain regions. In comparison to the control and vehicle groups, the administration of STZ resulted in decrease of GSH in several areas of brain.

Figure 7 illustrates how donepezil significantly ($P < 0.01$) reduced the drop in GSH levels in the areas of the cortex and hippocampal tissues. Plant extract administration stopped the STZ-induced drop in GSH levels. The GSH levels in the rat brain areas treated with STZ were considerably elevated by extracts of AM, AG, and LN.

Fig.7

Effect of PHF on AChE level in STZ-induced amnesic rat brain

The treatment of STZ increased the activity of AChE in the treated animals' hippocampal and cortical areas, according to the results. In rats injected with STZ, donepezil preventive therapy markedly reduced AChE activity in the cortex ($P < 0.05$) and hippocampal ($P < 0.01$) (Figure 8). The administration of plant extract stopped the activity of AChE from rising. The AChE activity in memory-impaired rats was dramatically reduced by extracts of AM, AG, and LN. In the brain areas of the rats given 200 mg/kg PHF, there was a notable reduction in AChE activity (Figure 8).

Fig.8

DISCUSSION:

The prefrontal brain region or the temporal lobe are the first sites of pathophysiology for cognitive impairment. It might range from dementia to moderate cognitive impairment.²⁰ Electrochemical signaling serves as the foundation for learning and memory processes, functioning as a network within the brain. Biogenic monoamines, acetylcholine, amino acids, neuropeptides, and other gene families may all be involved in the signaling process.²¹ The brain's process of forming memories may be split into many sequential stages like those of acquisition, retrieval, consolidation, and, in certain cases, reconsolidation or extinction.²² The process of learning a new behavior is divided into four phases: retrieval, which involves accessing stored memory, reconsolidation, which involves reevaluating previously acquired knowledge, and extinction, which involves inhibiting stored memory.²³ While acquiring new information necessitates the serial acquisition of memory, memories may also be formed from prior knowledge. From a behavioral perspective, the memory slots that result from the interaction of two distinct memory traces are generalization and interference.²⁴ Because Ayurvedic Polyherbal formulation (PHF) makes extensive use of both phytotherapy and specific folk remedies, it was employed to improve memory in experimental behavioral animal models. The study's methodology was created to assess the potency of three herbs—*Adoxa moschatellina*, *Alpinia galanga*, and *Laurus nobilis*, as a brain tonic against mental diseases. These plants are also believed to be useful as herbal supplements for neurological problems. The use of herbs has presented various potential to develop novel medications for memory problems²⁵. The PHF was found to be beneficial in this cognitive behavioral investigation for improving the learning and memory processes of animals in several behavioral models, including SRT, MWM, PCT, and

EPM. The findings demonstrated that STZ causes animal memory loss during testing in several behavioral paradigms. According to reports, STZ replicates the biochemical characteristics found in animals. In animal models,²⁶ PHF was found to be beneficial in lowering STZ-induced toxicity (learning and memory impairment) and in restoring the biochemical and enzyme levels of MDA and GSH. PHF was also shown to be useful in lowering acetylcholinesterase metabolic enzyme activity. The animal brain's acetylcholine levels are raised by the test medication. In multiple behavioral research on the neuroprotective medications meant to stop the brain from producing free radicals. The development of cognitive deterioration is indicated by the production of free oxidative radicals.²⁷ PHF decreased AChE activity in a dose-dependent manner in the brain's cortex and hippocampal regions. Our results were consistent with the research of Parfitt et al. (2012), which found that the hippocampal development, organization, and storage of memories are facilitated by the hippocampal consolidation of information from short-term to long-term memory.

CONCLUSION:

The study's findings suggest that PHF improved cholinergic function, decreased oxidative stress, and improved behavior in rats treated with STZ to cure amnesia. PHF might therefore be a different medication for treating patients with memory loss or deficiency.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I wish to acknowledge the assistance provided by my university management and colleagues.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST: Nil

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